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***A Cleanliness Drive in India:
Assessment on its Psycho-Social Impact***

Abstract

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (a cleanliness campaign) was initiated in 2014 under the regime of the NDA government. As the name signifies, the term 'Swachh' denotes cleanliness in Sanskrit. In its nascent stages, the program attempted to ameliorate waste management – most predominantly open defecation and efficient utilization of resources. With the primary motive of having a hygienic surrounding environment for its people, the government of India initiated sundry cleanliness drives under this campaign. However, the conceptualisation and formulation of plans is one aspect – the praxis, i.e., the practical implementation of these plans is another important consideration altogether, which is perhaps the primary concern for the Government of India – for, if there is an inability to acquire mass involvement and participation then there is an automatic implication of failure.

By having a comprehensive understanding of the motivational factors and attitudinal characteristics that members of a given community harbor – it would be relatively efficient at gaining mass involvement. Consequently, by addressing those factors and formulating plans on the basis of such fundamental facets there could be an exponential rate of success for such programs. Adding on to the literature and knowledge, which pre-exists within this domain, the subsequent research can aid in the better understanding of social perceptual phenomena and the successful implementation of programs related to campaigns addressing such issues. The study undertaken had a sample size of 1000 respondents.

The findings of the paper suggest that the cumulative assessment across the concerned thematic factors (political, social, environmental and communicational) apropos the initiative indicate an effective social (r)evolution with respect to the perceptual notions of the sample population involved.

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Introduction

Waste management has been an imperative and perennial activity. It has been prevalent in various permutations and combinations from crude disposal techniques – since ancient Greece – to complex technological advancements in today's modern world. This has been in practice for the ubiquitous – to keep waste at bay and in check.¹ Although, before the onset of the modern waste management systems and the municipalities being involved in the previously mentioned conundrum, waste management techniques were fairly unsophisticated. They ranged from landowners having the responsibility of solely (and merely) the space that lined their own; and people littering onto the streets of their community – garbage left on its own accord to amass and decay in the immediate circumscribing environment.²

Along with the advent of the Industrial Revolution in the nineteenth century, there was an inescapable burgeoning of waste. Hence, as a repercussive response to this rapid expansion of waste, there was (and since has been) a managerial call to arms to handle the alarming augmentation of waste, which has led to the dawn of the so-called 'Age of Sanitation'.³ India has been hurtling rapidly towards large scale industrialisation and urbanisation, which has accordingly led to the escalation of population⁴; not only has this given birth to an immediate and incessant need to cater to masses with respect to housing and employment, but it has also given way to several crises as a consequence of the aforementioned population explosion. One such crisis being: environmental degradation.

Concerning its population, India ranks as the second most populated country in the world, following closely that of China, which is first according to the census bureau (2018). This unprecedented growth of population has led to a gargantuan strain on one's environment such, especially sanitation. Presenting, therefore, dire implications for the health of not only the people, but also the circumventing environment; as it becomes tougher to manage and implement appropriate measures.⁵ Moreover, within India, along with the rise in population, there has – in addition – been a steady shift and rise in the income and monetary lifestyles of the populace involved. This has led to an increased strain on waste generation and an inadvertent (and tectonic) swing in the waste constituency. That is, with the expected evolution of standard of living, the waste composition constitutes more of paper, plastic and metal elements⁶. Corollary to that, waste is, as a result, rather tougher to dispose, and thus more hazardous to its surroundings. In India the waste disposal activities fair on a moderately makeshift level, this involves incineration of chunks of waste in both rural as well as urban sectors. The predicament mentioned above is owing to the dearth of waste collection plans as well as the existent one's being veritably inadequate.⁷

In India the Ministry of Environment and Forests and Climate Change (MoEF), Ministry of Urban Development, Central Pollution Control Boards (CPCBs), State Pollution Control Boards (SPCBs) and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) govern the management and parameters of health.⁸ Some of the provisional waste management programs introduced in India, within the past two decades, are as follows: National Waste Management Committee (1990), Strategy Paper (1995), Policy paper, Master plan of municipal Solid Waste (1995). All of these programs aimed at confronting the various realms of waste.⁹

The attitude of an individual, within a collective state, may reflect the attitude of the nationality one might associate with. The societal attitude in India is impacted and influenced by the caste system and economic status to quite a large extent which often inhibits the overall need for change.¹⁰ This complex and synergistic dynamic of religions and customs, which are rather politically charged, are often difficult to circumvent. This problem needs to be observed under the plight to reform the Open Defecation predicament, which, too, is religiously charged.¹¹ There were also sundry sanitation intervention programs introduced within India. In order to have a systematic way of not only making the masses cognizant about the dire consequences that unhygienic sanitary conditions induce, but to also make active efforts towards building a conducive environment to bring about change. One such measure implemented – which encompasses the protection of the health of the masses as well as the environment– with respect to hygiene and sanitary requirements, is Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (SBA) 2014.¹²

While people attempt to keep their households clean, the lack of ownership, accountability and responsibility of public spheres often leads to the littering of the same. It is then fundamental for communities to be conscious of the rationale behind SBA in order to realise the desired perceptual, attitudinal and consequentially behavioral change; which is why the Government of India has attempted to popularise SBA through modes of mass media such as social networking sites and the immanent influence of celebrities.¹³

The thematic focal point of the given research study was to assess the impact SBA had amongst the masses of Gandhinagar, in particular, with respect to their attitudes and motivational factors. With the sharp shift in the current contours of the environmental scenario vis-à-vis the modern world, it has become an imperative to harness the absolute power of mass momentum and not simply introduce sundry cleanliness campaigns.

Rationale of the Study

The study aims to examine the range of the conundrum, which is to assess the factors that are allegedly inhibiting the propagation, and the probable efficacious

enactment of the program. Correlating the expanse of it with key variables of the given study, which are: Societal Attitudes and Behaviours (attitudinal perception towards cleanliness campaigns aimed at environmental betterment), and Motivational Factors, which is corollary to the first variable. Under the above-mentioned variables, the study further probes the particular sub aspects that are associated with the said core variables, such as the openness that the masses hone towards certain plans and ideologies propagated and implemented for the improvement of the environment – under SBA. While taking into consideration the surrounding social, political and personal scenarios as well as narratives of people regarding the ones associated with the campaign and its implementation.

By analysing these variables, in context of cleanliness campaigns initiated by the government of India, the study aims to delineate why certain plans aimed at the betterment of the environment – which have calamitous consequences if not followed – are ignored by the masses. This study endeavors to examine the attitudinal differences, and hence motivational differences, if any, that occur within the sample population of the city Gandhinagar.

Potential Navigation of the Problem

Adding on to the subsequent research in this domain - this research aims to study the societal attitudes that invariably lead one to the motivational factors. Motivational factors, which either deter an individual from taking an active step, hence participation, or that which propel movement and action amongst the masses to actively participate, and endeavor to make a change.¹⁴

This study has been conducted vis-à-vis India's national movement – Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. By attitude, the study would aim at measuring the openness which the masses have been pertaining to the acceptance of an idea/movement in the direction of cleanliness management.¹⁵ By a nuanced analysis of the existing scenario of the country with reference to such campaigns, the study would aim to probe the dynamic of *Requirement v/s Delivery* within the city of Gandhinagar. With the help of analysing these variables, in the context of waste management, the study aims to understand why certain programs aimed at the betterment of the environment, and which hold dismal outcomes if not paid heed to, are neglected by the masses.

Objective of the Study

Waste management is an essential conduit towards the realisation as well as the actualisation of the goal of sustainable development. The two crucial components for its actualisation are: (i) application of regulations; and, (ii) engaged citizen contribution.

The need for comprehension of the populace perceptual lens as well as behavioral components – with respect to cleanliness and circumferential environmental health – is rudimentary in order for the latter to materialise the former mentioned component.

There is a configuration of hard built consumerism in the minds of people of this world. So much so that, there is a component of ‘benefit’ attached to each transaction and a self-satisfying purpose enlaced with each indulgence (of activity). Hence, there is an urgent need to make the aspect of private participation, especially concerning environmental health, attractive so that it is accomplished by a layered understanding of the psychological proceedings of the masses.

Urban regulations and policies have been in rotation for quite some time now, but most of them are known to tackle events and incidents in seclusion. There is a need to incorporate, include and assimilate the various aspects of what is known to be the environmental degradation and sanitation to have a holistic game plan.¹⁶

According to Venkateswaran (1994),¹⁷ there are sundry technological advancements that have set precedence for the way the conundrum of waste management system is (and should be) tackled. But the predicament of waste management is not simply confined to the superficial act of cleaning and/or the alleged semblance of cleanliness; but, also the additional componential factors that make up the issue: economical, political and social. One such development that is noticeable and praise worthy concerning SBA is that it seeks to integrate the different facets of waste management and include within it the awareness campaign – attitude (people) oriented.¹⁸ Swachh Bharat has kept in its repertoire an indicator to help set the parameters of the campaign and keep the objective in focus. It calls it the ‘IEC campaign’ (Inform, educate and communicate). This IEC is to be achieved through the dissemination of information via the mediums of mass media and interpersonal communication with the masses in order to activate them and their ideals (Urban Management Centre, 2014).¹⁹

The effects of the campaign in question and its impact are precisely what this paper seeks to study and comprehend within a nutshell. To elucidate further, the primary objective of the given study is to understand the penetrative power of the campaign ideals within the concerned community of Gandhinagar. Ergo, map effectively the attitudes and thus the motivation of the residents involved efficiently. Further, the secondary objective of the study is to suggest the key elements that set down the probable precedence for the future of cleanliness drives with respect to perception and attitude.

Methodology of the Study

The research methodology consists of an overview of the following components: Framework (design); measurement instruments; sampling & sample population.

Design

The design implemented for the following study was descriptive design. The hypothesis was built after the due assessment of the data collected. Data collection was observational in nature and included the utilisation of survey method in order to collect data.

Instruments

The study employed the following questionnaires:

1. Socio-economic Scale (SESC) by Kalia, A.K & Sahu, S (2012).²⁰ The self-report questionnaire was administered to the residents of Gandhinagar. The socio-economic scale is a 40-item assessment tool, which measures the socio-economic status of the participants across five parameters. Those parameters are: socio-cultural component; economic component; possession of goods and services; health component and educational component. The self-administered test takes approximately 20-25 minutes to complete (Kalia, A.K. & Sahu, S, 2012).²¹
2. Qualitative (apperception) measure to map perceptions on Swachh Bharat Abhiyan was designed and administered to the subjects. The questionnaires were administered to respondents irrespective of age, the exclusion criteria being 13 years and below. Questionnaire preparation – the first questionnaire was an existent psychometric test, the third questionnaire was customized and formulated to capture the essence of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan and were administered face-to-face.

Thematic Breakdown of Qualitative Measure

The developed measure consisted of 20 statements, which were formulated in sets of four componential spheres of evaluation (Political, Environmental, Social (Personal), and Communicational Activity), consisting of five questions each. The respondents were required to express their opinions towards the statements. The question sets probed the perception of masses chiefly to comprehend how the aforementioned individual components (parts), which were associated with SBA, had interacted and contributed in shaping public opinions towards the overall campaign itself.

The responses to each question were segregated into three broad strains that helped analyse and get an insight into the perceptual background of the concerned sample size. The three broad categories of measure for the responses of participants were divided into Enthusiastic Acceptance, Acceptance with Reservation, and Complete Rejection. An analysis group was formulated to comprehend the conclusions derived from the analysis of respondent's responses that were coherent and agreed upon.

Sampling and Sample Population

The sampling method applied was that of probability sampling called simple random sampling.

The sample size (n) was 1000 subjects residing in Gandhinagar. Random Sampling was chosen – with the prerequisite of them being residents of the city of Gandhinagar – care was taken to have appropriate number of participants from across various sectors of the city. The questionnaires were administered by the preferred method of face-to-face.

The sample included the average distribution of 512 males and 394 females, out of which 94 participants did not respond to certain sections of questionnaire set. The given sample varied across age, gender, family type, and educational qualifications. The sample population was then profiled on the basis of gender and the consequential perceptions with respect to the same. There were not significant distinctions and/or attitudinal differences found contingent upon gender and its contrasting social roles with respect to the environmental cleanliness initiative.

Inclusion Criteria

- (a) Participants residing in Gandhinagar
- (b) Participants above the age of 13 years
- (c) Vernacular – English & Gujarati

Exclusion Criteria

- (a) Age cap (max. limit) was undefined
- (b) Non-natives not considered

Discussion

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has been a pioneering campaign in laying the groundwork for many environmental pre-requisites since its initial introduction. Although, its impact seems to be intermittent and inconsistent when viewed from the pivotal point of active participation from respective masses. Mass

participation is an important precursor for attaining success in terms of *any* movement that is contingent upon community action: such is the case with most campaigns. The cumulative public perception towards a program is a compelling factor worth consideration that can help determine its subsequent success or failure. The barriers that pose a peril to the participative crucial constituent are those produced by either ignorant and/or erroneous judgment of the masses towards the components of the campaign or the entire campaign itself, or the ineffectual message dissemination from the campaign managers that includes the form of message propagation. While injecting campaigns of mass importance it is necessary to incentivize programs as well as provide people with a sense of accountability as well as responsibility in order to elicit active engagement.

Further, while evoking sentiments of onus upon the masses, it is necessary to take into consideration the preliminary perceptual background of the target populace - with respect to the given phenomenon/trend/objective – in order to estimate and appropriately customise a form of plan of conduct. Working according to which correspondingly helps drive the objectives and rationales of the concerned campaigns in a manner that seeks to mobilise the masses towards action - effectively. An erroneous/uninformative and/or even banal approach towards the same can lead to actions that are antithetical to the original sentiment of the mission. While assessing the perceptual background of the public involved can prove to be a tricky ordeal – owing to the subjectivity of the component – the enactment and subsequent consequences of actions (of the people) are indicators of the driving perceptions of the said populace: further used to circumvent the trend of common perceptions and confront them accordingly. During the assessment of perceptions of the masses towards Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, in the city of Gandhinagar, a string of common trends and opinions, with respect to the four different contributing factors, were cited repeatedly, which provided an acute insight into the reasons for its tremendous success within certain areas and its lack of thereof in the other.

Additionally, the propagation of these particular trend can be traced back to how a campaign, in general, is perceived. A campaign, when introduced, is seldom divorced from the various factors that construct it and/or drive it. The people connected to it, its objectives, its requirements, its rationale, its influence or impact – all these factors seem to build a communal perception towards the mission in the minds of people. A similar trend can be observed vis-à-vis the SBA, which was introduced by the Government of India in lieu of the deteriorating environmental scenario in context of India. People's perception towards the initiative was driven by the many factors (major themes) that

supported the campaign and its impact namely, their perception towards: (i) the promotional activities; (ii) the political affiliations;²² (iii) its impact on the environment; and, (iv) its impact on personal choices (peoples’ perception with respect to the overall societal change with regard to initiative). The perceptions towards these ideas were divided into three strains of ideas (sub-themes): Enthusiastic Acceptance, Acceptance with Reservation, and Complete Rejection as depicted in the tabular representation below (Table 1.0).

Table 1.0: Themes (of Campaign) and their Sub-theme Percentage Representation

<i>Thematic factors</i>	<i>Promotional Activities</i>	<i>Political Affiliations</i>	<i>Environmental Impact</i>	<i>Personal Choices</i>
1. <i>Enthusiastic Acceptance</i>	62.3%	54.19%	78.13%	88.4%
2. <i>Acceptance w/ reservation</i>	4.75%	11.43%	10.32%	4.6%
3. <i>Complete Rejection</i>	32.95%	34.38%	11.55%	7%

The table provides a descriptive depiction of the trends concerning people’s perception towards the initiative and its (4) components. These perceptions will further be classified as well as discussed below in detail by the aid of an illustration.

Fig 1.0: Fishbone (Ishikawa) Diagram

The Fishbone (Ishikawa) diagram illustrated below provides a brief overview of the relationships concerning the aforementioned factors (broad themes) and the most commonly occurring opinions (sub-themes) regarding each of them. These opinions of people, on a general spectrum, have a massive impact on the execution of the said campaign: SBA.

Views (beliefs and perceptions), with respect to certain phenomena, are seldom formed in isolation of an event, but are rather shaped and determined by the political, cultural, social, as well as identity-driven narratives. These factors have a strong influence not only on the creation of these perceptions, but consequently also have an impact on the receptivity of certain facts concerning the phenomenon.²³

From the diagram above, it can be observed that the overall perception towards Swachh Bharat Abhiyan mission was predominantly compelled by the perception towards political affiliations; the means and manner with which the sentiment of the campaign was projected; the impact on the environment since its introduction; and the impact on personal and societal choices after its introduction.

A process of identification and labeling of statements was performed – responses from sample population – which were exemplary of certain thematic ideas identified. Along the lines of the major themes – which the questionnaire probed – trends (sub-themes) were charted in accordance to the major themes to understand the prominent perceptions toward each. Such sub-themes were delineated by three streams, which grouped most responses towards the mission and its associated components.

The first theme explored (from top right) is that of promotional activities and their resulting impact on public opinion towards SBA. This thematic idea was sub- categorised into three prevalent trends according to the gauged participant responses, namely: *Party Propaganda*, – wherein subjects assumed that introduction of the campaign was a strategy by a concerned party to gain momentum and voters by capitalising on public favouritism. The second trend – *Publicity Stunt* – was observed as another major sub-theme estimated from the responses of sample population –this was with respect to many eminent personalities associated with the campaign to give impetus to and promote SBA and its cause. People’s perception towards the said celebrity involvement, trying to associate with an environmental cause, was that of an underhanded motive guided by a desire to gain for personal reasons in terms of attaining positive PR. The third perceptual trend spotted was that of *Commendable Efforts* by the government concerning the promotional activities conducted by them.

A positive response towards the governmental promotional activities, seen by the people, as an active effort towards mobilising masses as opposed to being a hidden agenda for other questionable reasons.

A possible way in which confidence of people might be attained and augmented, could be through co-creating the meaning of a campaign – in order to instill confidence amongst the masses and strive towards a successful implementation. Taking into consideration the *responsiveness* of the population, with respect to the campaign, whether positive or negative, traction towards the said campaign could be determined – which is important evidence to measure in order to discern the effects.²⁴ The value that it provides to its receivers is another important element that needs to be emphasised and addressed, to attract mass attention and participation to obviate negative judgments.^{25, 26}

The second theme explored was political affiliations and their consequent impact on public perception. Three principal sub-thematic ideas were observed with respect to that of political affiliations (attached with/to SBA); herein the sentiment (sub-themes) of masses ranged from High Skepticism, Moderate Skepticism, and Low and/or No Skepticism of the political affiliations. This reflected the opinions that the crowd held about their confidence in (governments) intent – the reasons behind the campaigns initiation, as well as the motives for realising its objectives. Within high skepticism, the involvement of any government official is viewed with great suspicion, owing to the belief that there was direct political connection with clandestine operations and/or propaganda of party propelling tactic. Moderate skepticism was a form of healthy skepticism, wherein the participants were not entirely skeptical, but were not all-too-trusting either. Low and/or No skepticism was a signifier of complete trust in the actions of Government and its officials and no reservations regarding their association with the campaign.

Perceptual biases are a common issue, which need to be tackled when employing a strategy that requires mass momentum – as they (biases) can distort the very inherent outlook regarding the action assumed. Perceptual biases are especially widespread in lieu of political discourse – there exists a negative associations attached with ‘politics’ as a terminology as well as an ideology.²⁷ This is especially true vis-à-vis the modern narrative of political discourse – where an air of cynicism is always dominant, and one common inference drawn is that of *corruption* – which is assumed to be “environmental phenomena” in terms of politics, perhaps due to the lack of credibility.^{28, 29, 30} There is a probability that if a similar initiation was undertaken by an NGO or other not-for-profit organisation, then it probably wouldn’t have had negative perceptual biases

adhered to it – which could be owing to having an anti-corruption outlook when the following type of organisations are in question. This could perhaps be an indicator of perceptual association germinating from, and rooted in, as a result of the influence exerted thus by the social institutions (and their established nature).³¹

The third theme explored was that of environmental changes and its impact on perceptions. According to an article published in Rajasthan Patrika (2019)³² – data interpretation attained from the people interviewed (residents of Gandhinagar) for the initial report from which this paper is derived - it was found that almost 70% people believed that SBA had shown tangible results concerning the surrounding environmental cleanliness. One of the trends observed from the participant responses was that of *visible and swift progress* achieved since the inception of SBA. Another trend observed was that of *slow progress*, wherein people stated that the progress was happening, but it was slow and sporadic in nature. The third sub-theme explored from the responses was people's opinions that there was absolutely *no progress* since its advent (of SBA), i.e. there was no tangible change seen in the environmental cleanliness.

The fourth theme explored was that of the impact on personal and societal choices, and people's opinions with regards to SBA as a result. The three sub-themes, most commonly surfacing, from the responses of the participants were that of strong initiative, wherein the subjects believed that there was a sense of durable effort towards the aims and objectives of SBA. The second common theme observed was that of lack of initiative and no tangible results observed thereby concerning the overall mass-mobilisation towards the materialisation of said goals of the program via the works of communal effort. The third sub-theme witnessed was a neutral (no opinion) stance. From the participant pool, sizeable portions of subjects were youth, and it was observed that most of them had been a part (concerning responses) of the first theme – *strong initiative*. When probed further it was attributed and supported by virtue of their own personal/individual contributions, which were by means of message dissemination by social media and its tools.

Personal traction and self-positioning one through the lens of social media is known to be a great precursor – in today's age – for motivating the current youth towards becoming more active on certain issues. This helps them in enhancing self-expression, forming of stylistic statement, success, and consequently towards self-identification and awareness of own abilities.^{33, 34} This has been observed as one of the many reasons for the youth in India being especially motivated in keeping a mindful presence on social media – by virtue

of its impositions. The youth is thus encouraged to voice concerns and opinions on current matters that aids in the effective diffusion of messages as well as help propel the cause further within the concerned focus group of one's unit.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The conundrum of unwarranted waste management has led India away from the conduit of achieving a clean and healthy society. SBA has attempted to make changes in the sphere of waste management – most predominantly open defecation and the efficient utilisation of resources, as the name suggests. Though the conceptualisation and formulation of intervention plans are the primary steps – the Praxis i.e. the practical implementation of the concerned drives is the primary concern for the Government of India too; for, if there is an inability to acquire involvement and participation from the masses, it hints at an inadvertent downfall of the respective program. Sustainable programs require a sustainable contribution.

Society functions on the postulates of structural functionalism, i.e. the various blocks of society need to function in consolidation and unison in order to foresee constancy and camaraderie. In pursuance of the former, there is a need to break the bounds of theoretical considerations and move towards the realm of practical implementations. The objective of Swachh Bharat is far from its point of culmination, but it is on the path of a steady ascent, which is towards the dream that Mahatma Gandhi once mapped. There needs to be a call to action towards the betterment of the societal conditions that we now live in.

As more than half of the Indian population is youth, and the youth is the future of a concerned country at any given point of time, it is an imperative to build upon and fundamentalise the environmental education of students in and outside classrooms – to assist in charting a future towards improved and wholesome ecosystem.³⁵ Although, one issue that seems to persist and will continue to, if not dealt with suitable regulations, is that of implementing the Swachhta index amidst the gaping aspect of measurement for alleged improvement. Thus, the difficulty is setting the occasional un-realistic (and idealistic) parameters of cleanliness, and the obscurity in achieving it.³⁶

There is an initiative that has been launched by NITI Aayog, which is an urban management program. This initiative seeks to implement measures for “Urban rejuvenation” in three key areas, one of them is urban solid waste management. It is in partnership with Singapore Cooperation Enterprise (SCE). The primary agenda of this collaboration was to take the professional assistance of experts from Singapore – in a plight to improve and face challenges that are

plaguing India in the aforementioned arenas. One particular key take away from the seminal dialogue between NITI Aayog and SCE was the recognised need to structure PPP (Public Private Partnership) within the Indian context vis-à-vis solid waste management. That is, to have the private sectors take upon them the onuses to manage the technological game play as opposed to the Government (Public) sector.³⁷

According to Delmon (2015),³⁸ the management of waste and environmental cleanliness is an imperative that needs an impetus and a colossal shift within the very manner in which it is dealt with. He proposes a phrase: “Turn trash into treasure.” He propounds that revenue opportunities can be generated by the in-cooperation of trash, i.e. by imposing tax on corporations and companies that produce waste, or Energy fees, Recycling fees – to provide value for recycled goods in markets where they can be employed and are useable.

There are sundry promising ways in which waste can be managed and the sanctity of sanitation levels within the country can be maintained. A time bound planning and implementation of regulations on the basis of analysis and active citizen participation – which is tackled with the help of behavioral understanding – is the need of the hour.

Limitations

The research does not take into account the various religious connotations, which are *one* of the most important, if not *the* most important, aspects of understanding perceptual notions towards (the delineated) phenomenon – especially among masses of India. Additionally, the study’s purview is concentrated and limited to that of one city as opposed to that of the entire nation. As India is a diverse country, it would be of great significance to conduct similar analysis pan India.

Notes

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